

Sustainable Development and Functional Characterization of Bamboo Lyocell/Cotton Blended Knitted Fabrics

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Abstract:

Bamboo lyocell fiber had gained global recognition for its sustainability and functional performance. In this experimental work there is analysis and characterization of four types of knitted fabrics having blend compositions such as 100 % bamboo lyocell, 100 % cotton, 70:30 bamboo lyocell/cotton, and 50:50 bamboo lyocell/cotton. The yarn and fabric samples were analyzed for their functional properties such as pilling resistance, dimensional stability (shrinkage), air permeability, water vapor transmission, and wicking behavior. The one way ANOVA results indicate that fiber blend proportion significantly influences most of the evaluated fabric properties. No significant effect was observed for shrinkage in the wale direction ($p=0.9820$). However, course-wise shrinkage, air permeability, water vapour permeability and wicking behavior exhibited highly significant difference ($p<0.001$). Fabrics with higher bamboo content demonstrated a more pronounced effect on these performance characteristics. The findings of experiment revealed that the 100% bamboo fabric exhibited superior air permeability ($125\text{cm}^3/\text{cm}^2/\text{s}$) and water vapor transmission ($5.88\text{ g/m}^2/\text{day}$), outperforming other blends. Results highlighted the potential of bamboo lyocell and bamboo lyocell/cotton blends to deliver enhanced moisture management and breathability, offering sustainable solutions for both performance and casual wear applications. The functional performance had shown that the bamboo lyocell's may be potential source of sustainable, high comfort alternative in knitted apparel fabrics, offering significant environmental benefits.

Keywords: Bamboo lyocell, Cotton and blends, Permeability, Shrinkage behavior, Sustainability

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1. Introduction

In present scenario, sustainable textile production is in demand and it is driven by growing environmental concerns. There is growing consumer demand for eco friendly and high-performance apparels. Conventional cotton cultivation requires consumption of natural resources such as approximately 7,000–29,000 L of water per kilogram of lint [1-4]. Besides high-water requirement, pesticides and fertilizers were also consumed in cotton production, contributing to soil degradation and environmental stress [4, 5]. Regenerated bamboo lyocell, had gained importance for their environmentally responsible production methods and favourable functional characteristics [6-8]. Bamboo lyocell fibre is produced via a closed-loop solvent spinning process using N-methyl morpholine-N-oxide (NMMO), which is nearly 99% recyclable, thereby minimizing chemical discharge and water usage. The resulting fibre exhibits excellent moisture and air permeability and a soft tactile feel, making it suitable for many applications, such as sportswear, leisurewear, and intimate apparel [9-11].

Recent studies had explored the potential of blending bamboo lyocell with cotton fibre in different ratio, aiming to combine bamboo's superior breathability and moisture-wicking capabilities with the mechanical properties of cotton fibres. Several researchers had studied bamboo/cotton knitted fabrics, and reported improved air permeability and reduced surface imperfections compared to pure cotton

fabrics [12, 13]. Similar studies had reported enhanced hand feel and reduced yarn faults in bamboo/cotton blends, supporting their potential application in premium apparel manufacturing. Some researchers had examined the mechanical and comfort properties of bamboo blends with other regenerated fibres, noting improvements in tensile strength, elastic modulus, and thermal comfort [14, 16-18].

Most studies and industrial applications had focused on bamboo rayon, while research on bamboo lyocell is now gaining momentum as sustainability concerns drive interest in eco-friendlier alternatives [15, 19]. Existing research had focussed on woven structures; while knitted fabrics, crucial for comfort remain under explore [12-14]. This study aimed to cover these gaps by systematically developing and characterizing four distinct knitted fabric compositions such as 100% bamboo lyocell, 100% cotton, 70:30 bamboo lyocell /cotton, and 50:50 bamboo lyocell /cotton. In this experimental work there were evaluation of functional characteristics such as pilling resistance, dimensional stability (shrinkage), air permeability, water vapour transmission, and wicking behaviour to establish correlations between blend composition and fabric performance.

2. Materials and Method

2.1 Fibres and yarn preparation

2.1.1 Fibres

The Lyocell fibre was procured from RSWM Bhilwara (Raj). Table 1 shows the fibre characteristics. In this experiment, it

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was tried to maintain constant fibre specifications in Cotton and Bamboo-Lyocell fibres, however the availability of fibre on commercial level produced some variability, which were statistically negligible. The important fibre properties which may affect the fabric comfort level were considered in this experiment as per table No.1.

Table 1: Fibre characteristics

Fabric Type	GSM	Thickness (mm)	Courses/Wales (inch)
100% Bamboo	150	0.45	31 / 30
50:50 Bamboo/Cotton	178.2	0.54	31 / 30
70:30 Bamboo/Cotton	172.8	0.59	52 / 40
100% Cotton	185	0.74	52 / 40

2.1.2 Yarn

The experimental work involved production of four yarn blends such as 100% Lyocell bamboo, 100% Cotton, 70:30 Bamboo/Cotton, and 50:50 Bamboo/Cotton spun to 30s count yarn, the different 30s yarn count were knitted and four fabric samples were produced. The yarns were spun using a ring spinning system to ensure optimal fibre alignment, uniformity, and tensile properties essential for achieving consistent loop formation during knitting. The different yarn properties were summarized in table no.3.

2.2 Fabric Manufacturing

Knitted fabrics were manufactured on TRYTEX Circular Knitting machine using the four different yarn compositions. The knitting machine settings, including a gauge of 28 needles per inch (28G) and loop lengths ranging from 2.5 to 3.5 mm, were carefully calibrated and validated prior to the sample preparation. Table 2 shows the fabric characteristics of four knitted fabric samples.

Table 2: Fabric Characteristics

Fabric Type	GSM	Thickness (mm)	Courses/Wales (inch)
100% Bamboo	150	0.45	31 / 30
50:50 Bamboo/Cotton	178.2	0.54	31 / 30
70:30 Bamboo/Cotton	172.8	0.59	52 / 40
100% Cotton	185	0.74	52 / 40

Tension control mechanisms were implemented to ensure consistent yarn feeding and uniform loop formation throughout the knitting process. For each yarn blend, preliminary trial runs were performed to optimize machine parameters.

2.3 Test Methods

The evaluation of yarn and fabric properties was conducted using international test standards. The yarn strength and elongation properties were measured with the Single Yarn Strength Tester following ASTM D2256. A total of five tests

were conducted. Yarn evenness and defects were evaluated using the Uster Evenness Tester following ISO standard procedures. The key parameters measured include Um% (mass unevenness), which reflects the variation in yarn mass along its length and impacts fabric uniformity; CVm% (coefficient of mass variation), a statistical indicator of yarn mass consistency; and neps, which are small entangled fiber clusters that contribute to fabric imperfections. The yarn twist level was evaluated by measuring Twist per Inch (TPI) and Twist per Meter (TPM) using a Twist Tester instrument in accordance with ASTM D1423 standard. Each measurement was conducted with a minimum of five test runs. Fabric thickness was determined using a Digital Thickness Tester following ASTM D1777. The Pilling resistance was evaluated with a Martindale Abrasion & Pilling Tester according to ASTM D4970. The samples were tested for 5000 rubbing cycles. The air permeability test is carried out to find the rate of airflow through a fabric by the Air Permeability Tester as per ASTM D737. Water vapour permeability finds the moisture transmission rate through the fabric, indicating its breathability and comfort level. The water vapour permeability of the fabric samples was determined with a Gester Water Vapour Permeability Tester in accordance to ASTM E 96. Wicking behaviour was assessed with a Vertical Wicking Tester based on AATCC 197. All tests were performed at least five times.

2.4 Statistical Analysis

A one-way ANOVA assessed the effect of blend ratio on each property at $\alpha = 0.05$. Where appropriate, F and p values are reported.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Effect on yarn characteristics

The yarns utilized for fabric development were manufactured from 100% Cotton and 100% Bamboo fibres, each exhibiting distinct morphological and mechanical properties as outlined in Table 1. Bamboo fibres, with slightly greater staple length (31 mm), higher denier (1.6), and superior tensile strength (24.2 g/Tex), were particularly suited for ring spinning process. The ring spinning is known for producing fine, strong, and uniform yarns with excellent fibre orientation [22]. The higher elongation percentage (4.5%) and maturity ratio (0.89) of bamboo fibre further contributed to enhanced spinnability and reduced neps during drafting, as confirmed by physical characterization (Table 3). Table 3 presents a comparative evaluation of yarn characteristics derived from varying bamboo/cotton fibre blends. Cotton fibres, though marginally shorter in length (29 mm) and having lower tenacity (21.6 g/Tex), were also blended with bamboo via ring spinning to maintain consistency in yarn structure and facilitate comparative analysis. The comparative assessment of yarns produced from 100% cotton, 100% bamboo, and bamboo/cotton blends demonstrates significant differences in mechanical behaviour and structural consistency, reflecting the inherent characteristics of each fibre type.

3.1.1 Twist parameters (TPI and TPM)

The analysis of twist parameters indicates that blended yarns exhibit higher twist per meter (TPM) values, ranging from 833.7 to 844, which surpass those observed in the 100% bamboo and 100% cotton fibre yarns. This enhancement in twist efficiency is associated to the improved inter-fibre cohesion between bamboo and cotton during the spinning process. The 50:50 bamboo/cotton blends demonstrate the highest TPM, suggesting the formation of a more compact and structurally stable yarn. The higher twist per inch in blended yarn resulted in stiffer fabrics as compared 100 % cotton and bamboo yarn fabrics. This indicate the 100 % pure cotton and bamboo fabrics are softer than their blends.

Figure 2: Effect of Bamboo/Cotton fibre blending ratios on (a) Single yarn strength and (b) Elongation %

Figure 1 shows that yarn twist parameters vary significantly with bamboo/cotton blending ratios. For 100% cotton, TPI (~20) and TPM (~800) are higher than 100% bamboo (~18 TPI; ~725 TPM), reflecting cotton's higher crimp and surface friction. From figure 1 it has been observed that there is no significance difference between both blend yarn samples. Both blend samples with 70:30 and 50:50 bamboo/cotton shows ~21 TPI and higher TPM ~825 and ~850, respectively. The increased twist in blends may result from the corresponding interaction of bamboo's smoothness and cotton fibre's convolutions, enhancing fibre cohesion and yarn compactness. These results indicate that moderate blending optimises twist characteristics, potentially improving yarn strength, uniformity, and processing performance in ring spinning applications.

3.1.2 Single yarn strength and elongation%

In case of single yarn strength, the 100% bamboo yarn exhibits the better strength, than the 100% cotton yarn and the blended yarn structure. This superior strength of bamboo yarn is due to inherent tenacity and extensibility of bamboo fibres as per table no.1. Among the blended yarn samples, the 70:30 and 50:50 bamboo/cotton compositions achieve a comparable strength value, indicating the mechanical integrity of the yarn were preserved at levels suitable for diverse textile applications as compare to 100% cotton .The synergistic cohesive force between bamboo and cotton fibres contributes to the overall performance of the blended yarns. Similarly, the good elongation % highlighted the mechanical advantages of bamboo fibres. The 100% bamboo yarn exhibits a significantly higher elongation value of 15.2%, compared to 4% for the cotton yarn. The better elongation % of bamboo yarn may be due to weaker cohesive force among the fibres that resulted in better elongation%. The incorporation of cotton into the blend resulted in a proportional decrease in elongation %, with the 70:30 blend yielding an intermediate value of 8%. This balance between elasticity and dimensional stability enhances the suitability of the blended yarns for robust and durable fabric constructions. The effect of bamboo/cotton fibre blending ratios on single yarn strength and elongation had been depicted in figure 2. These findings suggest that bamboo fibres contribute positively to both strength and elongation, whereas blending offers a balanced performance followed by optimising mechanical properties for diverse textile applications.

Table 3: Influence of Bamboo/Cotton Fibre Blends on Yarn Structural and Mechanical Properties

Yarn Type	TPI	TPM	Strength (gf)	Elongation (%)	Um %	CVm %	Thin (-50%)/Km	Thick (+50%)/Km	Neps (+280%)/Km	Hairiness
100% Cotton	20.39	801.82	325	4	9.61	12.14	0	20.25	13.75	7.52
100% Bamboo	19.1	752.6	348	15.2	9.42	11.86	0	3.22	4	6.50
70:30 Bamboo/Cotton	21.2	833.7	337	8	9.17	11.72	0	3.35	7.25	6.80
50:50 Bamboo/Cotton	21.5	844	332	6.5	9.21	11.77	0	4.5	9.3	7.00

Figure 2: Effect of Bamboo/Cotton fibre blending ratios on (a) Single yarn strength and (b) Elongation %

3.1.3. Evenness parameters and Yarn faults

The assessment of yarn evenness (Um% and CVm %) revealed similar performance across compositions, although the 70:30 blend shows the lowest CVm% (11.72), signifying improved mass evenness. The imperfection analysis presented in Table 3 had shown absence of thin places across all yarn samples, indicating effective control over the drafting process during spinning. The 100% bamboo yarn samples exhibited lowest level of yarn faults (imperfections), with zero thin places, (3.22) thick places/km and 4 neps/km, showing superior fibre uniformity and favourable spinnability. In contrast, the 100% cotton yarn exhibited substantially higher imperfections, with 20.25 thick places/km and 13.75 neps/km. These imperfections are likely associated with the shorter fibre length and lower fibre evenness as shown in Table 1. The blended yarns had exhibited intermediate imperfections, reflecting a balance between the properties of bamboo and cotton fibres. The increased proportion of cotton fibre in the blend may correlates with aincrease in yarn imperfections, signifying that fibre composition plays a critical role in determining yarn quality and uniformity. These results demonstrate that 100% bamboo yarn is characterized by superior single yarn strength, higher extensibility, and minimal imperfections, making it highly suitable for performance-oriented textile applications. In contrast, cotton yarn exhibits comparatively lower elongation and a higher frequency of yarn defects, which affect its mechanical and quality performance. In case of blended bamboo/cotton yarn samples, particularly those with 70:30 ratios, offer a balanced combination of mechanical resilience and uniformity, supporting their potential in functional and sustainable apparel manufacturing.

3.1.4 Hairiness

From Fig 3 the results had shown that 100% cotton yarn exhibited higher hairiness value (7.52), indicating a greater number of fibres ends protruding from the yarn surface. This can be attributed to the shorter fibre length distribution and higher cleaning intensity required during cotton blow room processing. In contrast, 100% bamboo lyocell yarn demonstrated lower hairiness (6.50), which might be linked to its smoother, more uniform fibre morphology and lower beating points requirements during blow room operations,

reducing fibre damage and surface distortion. The blended yarns (70:30 and 50:50 bamboo/cotton) had shown values in range of 6.80–7, suggesting that the incorporation of bamboo fibres had reduced hairiness of cotton yarn due to improved fibre packing and cohesion. From a sustainability perspective, lower hairiness in bamboo and blended yarns indicates a reduction in fabric defects such as pilling, leading to longer garment life and decreased fibre waste in subsequent finishing and usage stages.

Figure 3: Effect of Bamboo/Cotton fibre blending ratios on Yarn Hairiness

3.2 Influence of Bamboo/Cotton Yarn Blends on Fabric Performance Characteristics

The study investigates the influence of different fibre proportion in blended yarn on the functional performance of four different knitted fabric samples 100% bamboo lyocell,

Table 4: Comparative Analysis of Fabric Characteristics Developed from Varying Bamboo/Cotton Yarn Blends

Test Parameters	100% Lyocell Bamboo	100% Cotton	70:30 Bamboo / Cotton	50:50 Bamboo / Cotton
Abrasion Resistance Rating (1–5)	4	3	3-4	3-4
Pilling Resistance Rating (1–5)	3-4	3-4	3-4	3-4
Shrinkage Course wise (%)	14	12	10	14
Shrinkage Wales wise (%)	1	1.5	1	1
Air Permeability (cm ³ /cm ² /s)	125	100	115	110
Water vapor Permeability (g/m ² .day)	5.88	3.2	3.18	4.76
Wicking (cm/5 Min)	7.5	6.2	7.3	7.2

100% cotton, 70:30 Bamboo/Cotton, and 50:50 Bamboo/Cotton. Table 4 demonstrate trends in abrasion resistance, pilling behaviour, dimensional stability (shrinkage %), air permeability, and wicking behaviour of four samples.

3.2.1. Abrasion and Pilling Resistance

The 100% bamboo fabric exhibited better abrasion resistance rating (4), while the blended variants (70:30 and 50:50 bamboo/cotton) showed slightly lower ratings (3–4) followed by 100% cotton fabric samples. The poor abrasion resistance of cotton is due to the lower tensile strength and shorter staple length. The smoother fibre surface and longer staple length of bamboo fibre contributes to enhanced resistance against frictional force [4]. Pilling rating of all four samples were in the range (3–4), indicating that the yarn blend % had poor impact on surface fuzz formation. The constant value of pilling rating in all samples demonstrate that yarn spinning technique and fabric construction parameters played a more dominant role in controlling pilling behaviour rather fibre composition. Figure 4, demonstrates no significant difference in abrasion resistance of both blended fabric samples.

Figure 4: Effect of Bamboo/Cotton fibre blending ratios on Abrasion and Pilling Resistance of Fabric

3.2.2. Shrinkage Behaviour

From Table 4 & Fig.5 the Course-wise lowest shrinkage was observed in 70:30 bamboo/cotton blend (10%), followed by 100% cotton (12%), while both the 100% bamboo and 50:50 bamboo/cotton blends exhibited higher shrinkage at 14%. The improved dimensional stability in 70:30 blended fabric sample might be due to lower cotton's % as compared to 50:50 blend %. The higher moisture absorption in bamboo fibre contributed higher shrinkage in 100% bamboo and higher bamboo-content blends. The bamboo fibre has lower degree of polymerization hence higher number of reactive sites for water molecules absorption. Wales-wise shrinkage remained uniform across all samples (1%), suggesting that vertical dimensional changes are more influenced by knitting tension and loop configuration than fibre type.

Figure 5: Effect of Bamboo/Cotton fibre blending ratios on Shrinkage Behaviour of Fabric

3.2.3. Air and Water Vapour Permeability

From table 4 & Fig.6, the highest air permeability was observed in the 100% bamboo fabric (125 cm³/cm²/s), followed by the 50:50 and 70:30 blends (115 and 110 cm³/cm²/s, respectively), whereas the 100% cotton fabric

Figure 6: Effect of Bamboo/Cotton fibre Blends on Air Permeability and Water Permeability

show the lowest air permeability ($100 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^2/\text{s}$). The higher % of interstices between loop and wales of knitted structure and smoother surface of bamboo fibre improved airflow, whereas the dense inter yarn spacing due to strong cohesive force in 100 % cotton knitted fabric, decreased the permeability.

Water vapour permeability followed a similar trend, with the 100% bamboo sample depicting the higher transmission rate ($5.88 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{day}$) as compared to the 100% cotton samples ($3.2 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{day}$). The 70:30 blended fabric had shown lower vapour permeability ($3.18 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{day}$), indicated that increased cotton % decreased moisture diffusion due to increased cohesive force among fibres and increased binding of fibres. Figure 3 illustrated the influence of bamboo/cotton blend proportion on the air and water vapour permeability of knitted fabrics. These results suggested that bamboo-rich fabrics offer superior breathability and moisture management.

3.2.4. Wicking Behaviour

The wicking results presented in Table 4 & Fig.7 clearly indicate that fabric composition plays a crucial role in influencing moisture transport properties. The 100% bamboo sample exhibits the highest wicking height, reaching approximately 7.5 cm, which indicates superior capillary action and efficient moisture movement. The 70:30 bamboo/cotton blends show a slightly reduced wicking height of around 7.3 cm, suggesting the possible influence of cotton fibre which moderates the bamboo's inherent moisture transport capability. The 50:50 bamboo/cotton blend observed the wicking value, approximately 6.9 cm, reflecting further reduction in wicking efficiency as cotton content increases, which is further confirmed by the lowest wicking behaviour of 100% cotton (6.2 cm). These results suggest that as the proportion of bamboo fibre decreases, the ability of the fabric to wick moisture decreases. The naturally hollow structure and hydrophilic properties of bamboo enhance moisture transfer, while the denser morphology and lower absorbency of cotton as compared to bamboo lyocell limit capillary activity. Consequently, fabrics with higher bamboo lyocell content are better suited for end uses where rapid moisture movement and comfort are essential, such as sportswear and active apparel [6, 8].

Figure 7: Effect of Bamboo/Cotton fibre Blends on wicking behaviour

3.4 ANOVA Analysis

The one-way ANOVA (Table 5) shows the significance of fibre proportion on different fabric structures. The yarn blend composition significantly affects most fabric properties except shrinkage in the wale direction ($p = 0.9820$). Course-

wise shrinkage, air permeability, water vapour permeability, and wicking properties shows significant differences ($p < 0.001$), with bamboo-rich fabrics generally show greater significance as compared to other 100% cotton fabric samples in moisture management and breathability due to their higher hydrophilicity, capillary action, and hollow structure. The absence of variation in wale-wise shrinkage suggests that knitting structure dominates dimensional stability in that direction, while the strong influence of blend ratio on other parameters highlights the enhanced comfort-related performance in bamboo knitted fabrics.

Table 5: One Way ANOVA Summary for Fabric Characteristics across various Yarn Blends

Parameter	DF (Between)	DF (Within)	F-Value	P-Value	Significance ($\alpha=0.05$)
Shrinkage Course-wise (%)	2	12	97.89	0.0001	Significant
Shrinkage Wale-wise (%)	2	12	0.14	0.5255	Not Significant
Air Permeability ($\text{cm}^3/\text{cm}^2/\text{s}$)	2	12	16.20	0.002	Significant
Water Vapour Permeability ($\text{g/m}^2/\text{d}$)	2	12	462.61	0.0031	Significant
Wicking (cm)	2	12	34.76	0.0001	Significant

4. Conclusion

This study revealed that the yarn blend % significantly influenced many functional properties of knitted fabrics. The findings suggested that the 100% bamboo fabric consistently had exhibited superior air permeability ($125 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^2/\text{s}$) and water vapor transmission ($5.88 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{day}$), and outperforming other blends ($p < 0.001$). The 70:30 blend had shown significant improvement in shrinkage control (10%) compared to other samples. The fibre interaction (cohesive force) and fibre distribution in yarn affected wicking behavior and exhibited a similar trend in all samples. 100% bamboo fabric offers superior breathability, moisture management, and abrasion resistance, making it suitable for performance-oriented applications. The 70:30 blends had possessed better shrinkage control but compromises on wicking and vapor permeability. The 50:50 blends offers a balanced structure, offering moderate durability and comfort. The yarn blend composition had a statistically significant effect on the knitted fabric properties ($p < 0.001$), with no significant effect on wale wise shrinkage ($F(2, 12) = 0.14, p = 0.5255$). The higher elongation (15.2%), greater single yarn strength (348 gf), and improved yarn evenness (fewer thick places and neps) in the bamboo lyocell yarn's make it superior as compared to 100% cotton in various moisture management applications. Their superior moisture management, breathability, and wearer comfort make them a compelling choice for sustainable fabric development.

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